

PRACTICAL ASPECTS OF SOCIO-CULTURAL MANAGEMENT

Socio-Cultural Management Journal

Volume 3 (2020), Number 2, pp. 107-121

doi: <https://doi.org/10.31866/2709-846X.2.2020.222649>

p-ISSN 2709-846X, e-ISSN 2709-9571

Original Research Article

© D. Vasylenko, L. Butko,
V. Maslak, Yu. Domitrak,
2020

UDC: 005.342:069

JEL Classification: D73, I23, L30, M11, M15

Received: 25/09/2020

**Daria Vasylenko¹, Larysa Butko¹,
Volodymyr Maslak¹, Yuliya Domitrak²**

¹ Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, Kremenchuk, Ukraine

² University of Warsaw, Warsaw, Poland

The Role of Innovative Management Facilities in Museums Activities

Abstract: *Introduction.* The source of mechanisms of museums adaptation according to modern economy conditions lies in complete modernization of museum space based on strategic planning, scientific organization of management and implementation of new technological decisions in museum institutions activity. Specifically, the innovative museum technologies in the mix with modern management will guarantee the timely museum reaction on public requirements. A discrepancy in the instrumentation in its turn causes great reducing the level of attractiveness for modern user of museum services. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the study is the analysis of using facilities in innovative management sphere of museum institutions activities and its influence on museum industry development in context of culturally-educational museums activities. In order to solve the problem of research was used traditional complex of general scientific principles (determinism, reflection, unity of opposites) and methods (analysis and synthesis, systematic and structural, interrogation, content-analysis, observation, statistical). *Results.* This article presents the characteristic of concept “innovative management”. A special innovative management toolbox was found and it can also provide the background for some modernization in Ukrainian museum industry. Research results are confirmed by sociological survey based on theme “What would you like to see as a modern local history museum?”. *Conclusions and discussions.* Preservation of historical materials, popularization of knowledge, attraction wide circle of visitors – all these are the goals of any museum activity with the support of innovative management technologies. The use of innovative management has its nuances. Before starting work

with innovative toolbox implementation, one should think through its strategy, clearly define the goals; identify the target audience; prepare the media content etc.

Keywords: museum, innovation, management, technologization, popularization, re-branding, digitalization.

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. The museum sphere goes through dramatic fundamental changes, which cause the formation of new ideas in museum functioning as a special socio-cultural institution. Nowadays museums are getting more and more as resource-interpreters and resource-keepers, symbolizing the past and often helping the contemporary to find the inspiration, feeling confidence in the future. The modern Ukrainian museums face the task to integrate in new socio-cultural space, to learn some independency in financial aspects of their work. It becomes possible only if museum behaves itself as a unique socio-cultural object, able to cause interest in potential visitors by its inimitable image, reputation, competitiveness on socio-cultural service market.

In order to promote the museum brand for touristic, leisure-time and educational services, museums should learn the correct use of business cycle, in other words to learn the management, which gives the opportunity to modern museum science of how to create the completely new socio-cultural space, able to meet the modern society needs and show the individual socio-cultural trend.

Museum adaptation mechanisms as to modern economy conditions lies in complex modernization based on strategic planning, scientific organization of management, involving new technological decisions and museum technologies in the process of museum activity. The innovative museum technologies in complex with innovative management should provide the timely museum reaction on society requirements. Cultural-communicative approach and using of innovative technologies form the museum status as a cultural-leisure center. In modern world, with domination of technocracy and urbanization, the human specially needs the emotions, as conclusion we have a great concept change in relationships of human and culture, so in other words, the culture turns to be anthropocentric, as according to the *M. Kagan* (1996) – the human is the creator of its culture. In compliancy with it, the museum should provide the opportunity for the person to create the culture and produce emotions, because the museum itself as socio-cultural institution is obliged to react quickly on society requirements.

The technology of innovative museum management will give an opportunity to preserve its historical prestige and promote through translation of

social memory. The flexibility of museum management is the foundation for innovations in this field, the ground for modernization and adaptation for new, socio-cultural paradigm.

State study of the problem. The theoretical concepts, which lie in foundation of investigation were formulated on the basis of works of foreign investigators, which disclose the tendencies and perspectives of museums development in mix with innovative technologies promotion in XXI century: L. Bakaiutova (2008), N. Simon (2010), M. Rouse (2016), A. Murphy (2018), A. Mikhailova (2019). These studios suggest the conceptions of museums development in modern socio-cultural space open the multi-discipline foundation of process innovations and separate their functional, structural and socio-cultural parts.

The domestic investigations in the field of innovations in the museum business were actively growing on the very beginning of XX century, but did not have a systemic character. The theme of innovative museum development nowadays needs a fundamental theoretic-methodological analysis, which will allow answering the main questions of innovative museum field.

The investigations of problems, concerning innovative museum studies are conducting by M. Bielikova (2015), V. Banakh (2016), R. Mankovska (2016), O. Chervonyk (2018), V. Maslak and D. Vasylenko (2018), S. Rudenko (2018), S. Kuskova and O. Otzemko (2019), I. Parkhomenko (2019), etc.

The scientists emphasizes the importance of rebranding of Ukrainian museum system, its renewing by digitalizing in contex with museum management. The main problem of Ukrainian museum space is its inefficient management policy and lack of necessary funding, which causes mainly the decline of museums.

Unresolved issues. The modernization of museum institutions affects by socio-economic conditions, deep society transformation, which needs visualization and computerization of cultural inheritance. Nowadays, on modern level of development it comes, that museum visitor has new requirements. This causes museum modernization with the aim to preserve its socio-cultural status. These changes can't be superficial, because the involving of innovative technologies should have deep character, in other words, the essence of museums – its nomination, role and place in socio-cultural environment should be reviewed. That is why, the key questions, connected with innovative museum management must be investigated.

During the studying aspects of innovative transformations in museum institutions functioning needs to be analyzed. First of all, innovative museum management is investigated as a method of providing and supporting of per-

sonnel high quality work in museum institutions. In the second, investigations in sphere of innovative museum management are analyzed in context with museum activity coordination and its promotion on the service market. Thirdly, it is determined the role of properly formed strategy of planning digitalizing as a component of innovative museum management, which gives attractive opportunities of museum financial independence.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose of the article is an analysis of using the innovative management instrumentation in museums institutions activity and its influence on museum industry development in general and in context with cultural-educational museums activity.

For reaching the established goal, one should decide the following tasks:

- to reveal the concept of innovative management in museum sphere;
- to define the strategic purposes for museum modernization;
- to formulate the instrumentation of innovative management in context of museum modernization.

The methodological basis of the study became the concepts and theoretical-methodological approaches, which deal with museums as not only a wealth of cultural value, but as socio-cultural institution, providing their use in deciding modern problems of individual formation. The systemic approach characterizes the innovative museum management as an object of socio-cultural sphere, viewed through the lens of museum connection with its visitors, with the aim to meet the population demands, realization of educational-pedagogical and cultural- leisure museum activity.

Research methods. In order to solve the established tasks of the research was used a special complex of scientific and cultural methods of analysis, which was also applied in order to mark the general evaluation of modern museum science in the context of socio-cultural development, promoting the formulation of suggestions, connected with museums adaptations to new socio-cultural conditions.

Structural method is enabling to describe the peculiarities of modern museum institutions and formulate recommendations for the improvement of their activities, in conditions of new social demands.

By means of this method it was identified the level of innovational management implementation into activities of museum institutions. The method of situational research enables to explore the innovational management instrumentation, techniques and technologies in the process of museum adaptation as to socio-economic and cultural conditions of external environment.

Using the methods of analysis and synthesis, it was revealed the level of this theme awareness, considered the problems of modern museums development.

In the framework of the study, by means of SWOT-analysis, was evaluated the external environment and museum functioning there.

The research based mainly on the methods of social, socio-psychological, pedagogical and managing analysis, which were used during the respondents' questionnaire. All these gave an opportunity to define the level of necessity of digitalization in museums activity from a position of visitors. The method of examining enabled to consider the efficiency of the research in the field of innovational museum management and the level of visitors involving to museums activities.

Research information base. The problems of functioning and managing the museum science became more attractive for scientists and museum workers because of rapid processes of society development.

Nowadays the question of museum science restructuring is widely discussed. The theoretical bases of the research were scientific works of T. Yureneva (2003), Yu. Komlev (2005), V. Velykochoyi and N. Hasiuk (2005), M. Rutynskyi and O. Stetsiuk (2008), Z. Mazuryk and H. Aarts (2009), Ya. Martynyshyn and O. Khlystun (2018, 2019, 2020), Ya. Martynyshyn and Ye. Kovalenko (2017, 2018), S. Knell (2018).

The object of the research for articles author turns out to be the museum sphere in Poltava region. In this article, the authors explored the innovational technologies in museum activity, its interaction between visitors, and the satisfaction of clients, using the museum institutions. The research was conducted in 2019-2020 years. On the basis of using complex analysis the museum informational system, through collection of data, and in particular, questionnaire, by *Philipa Kotlera* (1996) method, the authors identified the main specifications for making decisions in building the typical model of museums modernisation and suggest the strategic directions of its improvement.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The innovational museum management as a factor of successful mission implementation

In the present-day world, the cultural-informational role of museums is extremely important, because they are factors of society development by means of historical levels imaging in social life and displaying the ways of perception. That is why, for museum institutions are rather important to choose the right strategy of managing, which enables to involve the wide range of visitors. For

today, one of the main priorities in work with modern museum is the promotion and using the technological innovations like parts of innovative management.

Through conceptual apparatus of museum management, let's give a concrete view on terms „management” and „innovational management”, in order to reveal better the concept of the last one. We start from the generally accepted term „management”, which required the system of principles, methods, techniques and means of production management, intellectual, financial and other resources.

According to identification of a concept „management”, one can formulate, what is namely the museum management – it is a system of principles, methods, techniques and means of governing the museum institution and its personnel.

While characterizing the concept „museum management” one should complete the peculiarity of museum as not-for-profit organization, its role in society is rather different from other commercial institutions (Soboleva, 1997).

That is why, the museum management considers being the system of governing, aiming at supporting the successful museum functioning in the process of which, a mission of museum can be fulfilled with developed interaction between the visitors (Lewis, 1986).

The successful implementation of museum mission in the contemporary society takes place, first of all, because of innovational management promotion. According to *Robert Taker* (quote of Klyachina, 2017), while fundamental changes happened in world, innovational practice in recent 20 years almost stayed the same, it's as earlier remain non-systematic, fragmentary and counted on „sleeves down policy”. So, because not every first manager (the director of museum) understands the importance of museum managing realization through innovational management techniques, which became an integral component of each contemporary museum. That is why, the innovational management turns out to be a special system of principles, methods and techniques, which involve target-oriented managing the processes of creating and promoting innovational technologies in the institution. In the framework of innovational management occurs plan formation of e-science and digitalization of museum institution.

The use of innovational management technologies connected with classical methods of museum governing plays a great role in realization communicational connection „museum – visitor”. The main problem in providing innovations in museum science remains the lack of enough financing, which causes first of all, the lack of special department or personnel, working with innovational museum development (this causes non-systematicity and fragmentary in museum activity); secondly, impossibility to involve any innovational projects, which can be proposed (this causes backwardness and non-modernity).

The main tasks of innovational museum management:

- the planning of innovational museum activity;
- the formation of processes and structures for maintenance of museum innovations;
- the motivations of digitalization participants;
- the systematic evaluation of results an innovational activity of museum institution.

It should be noted, that the efficiency of innovative management in museum activity measures with not only as non-commercial component, but also like socio-cultural concept for society. According to this, the innovational management should be realized because of museum resources: collections, personnel, accommodation, reputation, financing. However, the significant parts in the concept of innovative management are visitors' demands, as the chief recipients in museum resources. Assuming the contemporary position in Ukrainian museum science, especially in regions, it is necessary don't forget about request to change the course of innovational management from the state or private sponsor, that is not always justified and be useful for enhancement of museum development level.

Innovative management in museum must function as a part of target markets, in order to meet the demands of visitors, state, private sponsors and its own demands, to have the power to turn Ukrainian museum into popular touristic route. One more complexity in realization of innovative management is its non-commercial component, because such socio-cultural objects like museums cannot receive great profit as a result of their functioning.

The budget money, targeted for museums for their innovational development, is rather limited. The main part of financing covers the maintenance of nowadays activity, with the help of grants. Because of it, the financing of innovational projects from culture administrative bodies, as well as the regional and state levels take place according to residual principle. It is worth to mention the problem of diversification of financing sources in general, which usually face museums becoming self-sufficiency.

Lack of adequate funding causes the problem of deficiency of skilled personnel, who can intensify the process of providing and accompaniment innovational instrumentation due to museum functioning. Foreign museums decided such a problem with the help of cooperation with organizations and business, which were purposed to not only suggest the sponsorship, but also even to become an integral part of museum supervisory council. Therefore, the sponsors ensure their financial or professional resources, which provide technical and consulting maintenance of innovational museum instrumentation.

3.2. Technological instrumentary of innovational management: ways of implementation

Let us consider the ways of implementation of innovational management in the perspective of museum institutions activity. Large part of Ukrainian museums use the traditional forms of demonstration the so-called valuable museum pieces, which in contemporary „world of impression” do not affect the visitor (Gordin et al., 2014). In the past, the form of interaction between the museum and the visitor was considered through an excursion, conducting by museum worker. The modernity gives us new possibilities of communication between the visitor and the museum. There are lot of innovational instruments for making better the chain „visitor – museum”: web sites, accounts in social networks, interactive panels and screens, playing consoles, geo-informational systems and mobile tools.

Nowadays the museum visitors are interested in getting exceptionally bright experience, where real artifacts give unreally attractive impulse and really matters only memories, created by museum digitalization (Pine & Gilmore, 1998).

First, let us address specifically to web sites, holding the whole museum content, including articles, photos, videos, blogs, useful pages, advertising materials, etc. All content should be interesting and closely connected with museum activity in order to generate interest of potential visitor. The web site also can be the source of additional income for museum, if working rightly with advertising. However, one should be very careful with advertising, using only materials concerning socio-cultural activity.

According to site [statista.com](https://www.statista.com) the quantity of users of social network 01.01.2020, consist of more than 20 million (Ukrainskyi Spektr, 2020). That is why, the most important moment of innovational museum management is to create accounts in social network Instagram (16 million Ukrainians) and Facebook (19 million Ukrainian users). Because today great number of people, (60%) are using smartphones to seek interesting and enlightening places of rest. Therefore, the chief sources of finding are Internet applications. The advantages of social network are the following: their functional completion (opportunity to public the events from museum life, creating invitations and reminders for subscribers about expositions, performance-taking place in the museum).

The main idea of using digitalization is to find a close connection between the visitor and the museum. It is important to ensure visitors, that they can not only look through the exposition „from afar”, but also feel, experience it. There are many different gadgets, using for this: the playing consoles, QR-codes on the walls and shelves, video installations with beautiful sound, mobile radio systems, automatic guide, sensor stall and huge informational displays.

Advanced technologies, aiming at gaining self-experience through learning the exhibit and the events in comfortable conditions, not only see the interpretation of so-called exposition. The digitalization of museum space gives an opportunity to expand the exposition. For example, in conditions of limited area we can present the digitalized archival materials or huge library in reserve. By means of digitalization, the museum plays one of the important roles – the educational. For example, the schoolchildren, while visiting museum can draw the map of old Europe or to place on the map the architecture of their town, even their own home location.

Taking into attention the contemporary quick world, when in terms of the pandemics, the majority of people cannot visit museums, but they have an access to the Internet, the museum must aim at innovations, to give the visitor an opportunity to feel the exposition even sitting near the computer at home. It is very important to create such special conditions, waking in the visitor a sense of belonging to museum exposition; this can be possible only through using of geo informational systems and virtual excursions. The essence of geo informational systems lies in visitors opportunity to click the button in the site, or to use the mobile application look through geographical map with all museum locations, pictures, photo and audio materials (for example, The map of Kremenchug www.oldkremen.zzz.com.ua; the Pantheon of outstanding Ukrainians <http://ukrainelegend.zzz.com.ua/>) (Maslak & Vasylenko, 2018). The virtual exposition, implementing 3D technologies gives an opportunity to potential visitors to review the museum exposition in detail and this can be useful for pupils and students in educational goals without leaving a classroom.

During the research, aiming at confirming its results, a special questionnaire between students 2-4 courses, learning the specialty 02 Culture and Art was conducted: the question was „What you imagine in a contemporary local history museum?”. The respondents received the preform, including 4 questions, with answers „Yes” or „No”:

1) if it necessary for local history museum to have a web site and pages in social network Instagram and Facebook, full of video-, audio- and text content?

2) would it be convenient for you to use mobile application for reading QR code from the windows of the exhibits, where exponents are placed?

3) would you like, that local history museum become not only the place of preserving of historical memory, but also the place of conducting modern cultural performances, if even not always thematically connected with the museum?

4) is it necessary to enhance the local history museum, by means of innovative technologies or it can be left without changes, in classical view?

The overall quantity of respondents is 72 people. First question was with 91% of positive answers „Yes”, and only 9% think, that it is not necessary for a museum, to be presented in a global Internet network. 83% of respondents are ready to use the mobile addition for reading QR code from the exhibit windows, 12% had a negative attitude to the proposition. The idea, concerning cultural performances in a local history museum was popular between 95% of respondents, 5 % disliked the idea. 100% of respondents, taking part in the questionnaire agreed, that local history museum must be enhanced by means of innovational technologies (*Figure 1*).

Figure 1. The results of social questionnaire “What you imagine in a contemporary local history museum?”

Source: own design

It should be noted, that questioned respondents during 2019-2020 years attended museum institutions in Poltava region, which were the objects of our research as a part of excisional groups, in order to give the objective answer to posed questions. As we can see, the young people fall back on the belief, that the modernization of museum sphere, through techniques of innovational management is very important and must be realized within a short time.

4. Conclusions

Preserving the historical artefacts, the popularization of knowledge, involving wide range of visitors – the main objective of modern museum activity and innovation management technologies must promote this. Without implementing digitalization into the museum sphere on the modern level of society development it will be impossible in future to fulfil the socio-cultural function of museum. Museum effective functioning will be in danger. The using of methods and principles of innovative museum management gives a chance to enter a new level of development for museum institutions in Ukraine.

1. Under the concept “innovative museum management”, we understand the classical processes of museum governing and involvement new innovative systems, including digitalization of museum space for providing a normal life for museum institution.

2. Application the museum management has its peculiarities. Before starting a campaign with involvement, the innovative instrumentation in a museum, one should think over strategy to work with. Clearly identify and define the goals, draw out the target audience, prepare the media content (articles, video-, audio materials, presentations) etc.

3. Emphasizing the importance of specialists available, which can start implementing and using the innovative technologies. The readiness of museum personnel to use actively the innovative methods and forms of work, realization the principle of command work among museum personnel. Involvement for museums people-volunteers using out sorting principle, that will give an opportunity to collaborate with partnership authorities through promoting special actions, events at the museum base.

4. To attract additional funding, which can be aimed at using innovative technologies in the museum, we should cooperate with tour firms (“engagement” of tourists for museum to increase the income from selling entrance tickets and souvenir products), art facilities (the organization of exhibition of local artists), creative industry organizations (the rental of museum space for conducting different events, requiring special intimacy) etc.

5. Integrating and using simultaneously a few forms of digitalization in museum management, requiring steadily control, check and analyzing its collaboration with visitors.

6. Aiming at involving new groups of visitors, especially virtual, we should use the practice of conducting virtual events. For an example, the conducting of photo competition on the basis of web site and on museum accounts in social networks, the main condition of it will be the photo in the background of the museum exhibits. Consequently, the audience of visitors will

be enlarged, because the most active social network users have the age range at 14-35 years, so the museum will reduce an opinion, that only old people visit it.

Scientific novelty of the obtained results lies in the development of theoretical principles of museum management, including the complex of analysis methods, synthesis and systematization, for processing the problem of applying the new technologies of innovative management due to museum functioning and formulation the practical recommendations for their involving in everyday use.

The practical significance of the results obtained that formulated and proposed recommendations, propositions and conclusions can be implemented with the aim to solve the actual problems, concerning innovative management in museum activity and the popularization of museum institutions practical activity.

Prospects for further scientific exploration in this direction require further researching the question of development in museum innovative management, popularization of museum institution functioning, because it is the main condition for further museum development in Ukraine.

Acknowledgement

This research is fulfilled according to scientific theme of the Department of Humanities, Culture and Arts of Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University within the theme: „The peculiarities of functioning the institutions in socio-cultural sphere” (the Project #0120U103599).

References:

- Bakaiutova, L. N. (2008). *Modernizatsiia Deiatel'nosti Muzeev: Otechestvennyi i Zarubezhnyi Opyt (na Primere Muzeev Sviazi) [Modernization of the Activities of Museums: Domestic and Foreign Experience (on the Example of Museums of Communication)]. Avtoreferat Kandydatskoi Dysertatsii [Abstract of Thesis Candidate's Dissertation]*. St. Petersburg: SPbGUKI (in Russ.)
- Banakh, V. M. (2016). *Muzeini Innovatsii ta Interaktyvnist u Teorii ta Praktytsi Muzeinoi Spravy [Museum Innovations and Interactivity in the Theory and Practice of Museum Work]*. *Historical and Cultural Studies*, 3(1), 1-5 (in Ukr.).
- Bielikova, M. V. (2015). *Zaprovadzhennia Innovatsiinykh Tekhnolohii v Muzeiakh Ukrainy [Introduction of Innovative Technologies in Museums of Ukraine]*. *Naukovi Pratsi Istorychnoho Fakultetu Zaporizkoho Natsionalnoho Universytetu [Scholarly Works of the Faculty of History, Zaporizhzhya National University]*, 1(43), 326-330 (in Ukr.).

- Chervonyk, O. (2018, February 16). Arsenalnyi Modernizm [Arsenal Modernism]. *Korydor*, Retrieved from <http://www.korydor.in.ua/ua/opinions/arsenalnyi-modernizm.html> (in Ukr.).
- Gordin, V. E., Khoreva, L. V., & Dedova, M. A. (2014). Sovershenstvovanie Muzeinogo Menedzhmenta na Osnove Razvitiya Sobytiinnoi Deyatel'nosti [Perfection of Museum Management by Developing Event Activity]. *Izvestiya Sankt-Peterburgskogo Gosudarstvennogo Ekonomicheskogo Universiteta [Bulletin St. Petersburg State University of Economics]*, 4(88), 73-82 (in Russ.).
- Kagan, M. S. (1996). *Filosofiya Kul'tury [Philosophy of Culture]*. St. Petersburg: Petropolis (in Russ.).
- Klyachina, A. R. (2017). Informatsionnye Tekhnologii v Razvitiu Muzeinogo Marketinga [Information Technologies in the Development of Museum Marketing]. *Nauchnye Trudy Moskovskogo Gumanitarnogo Universiteta [Scientific Works of the Moscow University for the Humanities]*, 1, 23-27, doi: 10.17805/trudy.2017.1.3 (in Russ.).
- Knell, S. (Ed.). (2018). *The Contemporary Museum: Shaping Museums for the Global Now*. London: Routledge.
- Komlev, Yu. E. (2005). Organizatsiia Marketingovoi Deyatel'nosti v Muzee [Organization of Marketing Activities in the Museum]. *Avtoreferat Kandydatskoi Dysertatsii [Abstract of Thesis Candidate's Dissertation]*. St. Petersburg: SPbGUKI (in Russ.).
- Kotler, P. (1996). *Osnovy Marketinga [Marketing Essential]* (V. B. Bobrov, Trans. in Eng.). Moscow: Progress (in Russ.).
- Kuskova, S. S., & Otzemko, O. V. (2019) Suchasnyi Ukrainyskyi Muzei: Novitni Praktyky [Modern Ukrainian Museum: the Latest Practices]. *Visnyk Studentskoho Naukovoho Tovarystva Donetskoho Natsionalnoho Universytetu Imeni Vasylia Stusa [Bulletin of the Student Scientific Society of Vasyl Stus Donetsk National University]*, 11(2), 33-38 (in Ukr.).
- Lewis, G. W. (1986). Towards a Responsive Museum. *MUSE*, 4, 1.
- Mankovska, R. V. (2016). *Muzei Ukrainy u Suspilno-Istorychnykh Vykykakh XX – Pochatku XXI Stolit [Museums of Ukraine in the Socio-Historical Challenges of the XX – Early XXI Centuries]*. Lviv: Prostir-M (in Ukr.).
- Martynyshyn, Ya., Khlystun, O., & Blašková, M. (2020). The System as a Socio-Cultural Phenomenon Philosophy of Management. *Socio-Cultural Management Journal*, 3(1), 3-38.
- Martynyshyn, Ya. M., & Khlystun, O. S. (2018). Fenomen Idej v Upravlinni Zhyttiediial'nisti Suspil'stva [The Phenomenon of Ideas in the Management Activity of the Society]. *Visnyk Kyivs'koho Natsional'noho Universytetu Kul'tury i Mystetstv. Seriia: Menedzhment Sotsiokul'turnoi Diial'nosti [Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Management of Social and Cultural Activity]*, 2, 7-25, doi: <https://doi.org/10.31866/2616-7573.2.2018.149294> (in Ukr.).

- Martynyshyn, Ya. M., & Khlystun, O. S. (2019). Hierarkhiia yak Fenomen Orhanizatsijnoi Kul'tury [Hierarchy as a Phenomenon of Organizational Culture]. *Visnyk Kyivs'koho Natsional'noho Universytetu Kul'tury i Mystetstv. Serii: Menedzhment Sotsiokul'turnoi Diial'nosti [Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Management of Social and Cultural Activity]*, 2(1), 7-31, doi: <https://doi.org/10.31866/2616-7573.1.2019.170653> (in Ukr.).
- Martynyshyn, Ya. M., & Kovalenko, Ye. Ya. (2017). Smysly v Kul'turi Upravlinnia [The Measures in Culture of Management]. *Visnyk Natsional'noi Akademii Kerivnykh Kadriv Kul'tury i Mystetstv [Herald National Academy of Managerial Staff of Culture and Arts]*, 4, 26-31 (in Ukr.).
- Martynyshyn, Ya. M., & Kovalenko, Ye. Ya. (2018). Formuvannia Suchasnoi Systemy Upravlinnia Zhyttiediiial'nistiu Suspil'stva [Formation of the Modern System Management of Life Society]. *Visnyk Kyivs'koho Natsional'noho Universytetu Kul'tury i Mystetstv. Serii: Menedzhment Sotsiokul'turnoi Diial'nosti [Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Management of Social and Cultural Activity]*, 1, 7-24, doi: <https://doi.org/10.31866/2616-7573.1.2018.143383> (in Ukr.).
- Maslak, V., & Vasylenko, D. (2018). The Practice of Using Interactive Multimedia Installations in Museum Activity. *Visnyk Natsionalnoi Akademii Kerivnykh Kadriv Kultury i Mystetstv [National Academy of Managerial Staff of Culture and Arts Herald]*, 2, 67-70, doi: 10.32461/2226-3209.2.2018.161478.
- Mazuryk, Z., & Aarts, H. (Eds.). (2009). *Muzei: Menedzhment i Osvitnia Diialnist [Museum: Management and Educational Activities]*. Lviv: Litopys (in Ukr.).
- Mikhailova, T. B. (2019). *Menedzhment Muzeev [Museum Management]*. Ekaterinburg: UrFU (in Russ.).
- Murphy, A. (2018, January 30). Technology in Museums – Introducing New Ways to See the Culture World. *Museums + Heritage Advisor*, Retrieved from <https://advisor.museumsandheritage.com/features/technology-museums-introducing-new-ways-see-cultural-world/>.
- Parkhomenko, I. (2019). Skladovi Formuvannia Popytu na Kulturni Iventy Ukrainy (na Prykladi Muzeiv) [Creating a Demand for Cultural Events in Ukraine (on an Example of Museums)]. *Visnyk Kyivskoho Natsionalnoho Universytetu Kultury i Mystetstv. Serii: Menedzhment Sotsiokul'turnoi Diial'nosti [Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Management of Social and Cultural Activity]*, 1, 134-154, doi: 10.31866/2616-7573.1.2019.170662 (in Ukr.).
- Pine, B. J., & Gilmore, J. H. (1998). Welcome to the Experience Economy. *Harvard Business Review*, 76(4), 97-105.
- Rouse, M. (2016). Innovation Management. *WhatIs.com*, Retrieved from <https://searchcio.techtarget.com/definition/innovation-management>.
- Rutynskiy, M. Y., & Stetsiuk, O. V. (2008). *Muzeieznavstvo [Museology]*. Kyiv: Znannia (in Ukr.).

- Rudenko, S. B. (2018). Muzei v Nehatyvnomu Dyskursi Modernizatsii [Museum in Negative Discourse of Modernization]. *Visnyk Natsionalnoi Akademii Kerivnykh Kadriv Kultury i Mystetstv [National Academy of Managerial Staff of Culture and Arts Herald]*, 4, 178-183 (in Ukr.).
- Simon, N. (2010). *The Participatory Museum*. Santa Cruz, CA: Museum 2.0.
- Soboleva, E. S., & Epshtein, M. Z. (1997). Marketingovy Podkhod k Upravleniyu Muzeem [Marketing Approach to Museum Management]. *Kunstkamera Vchera, Segodnya, Zavtra [Kunstkamera Yesterday, Today, Tomorrow]* (Vol. 2). St. Petersburg: Muzei Antropologii i Etnografii Imeni Petra Velikogo (Kunstkamera), 166-202 (in Russ.).
- Ukrainskyi Spektr (2020, June 23). Naipopuliarnishi Sotsialni Merezhi v Ukraini ta Krainakh Svitu u 2020 [Most Popular Social Networks in Ukraine and Countries Around the World 2020], Retrieved from <https://uaspectr.com/2020/06/23/najpopulyarnishi-sotsialni-merezhi-v-ukrayini-ta-krayinah-svitu-2020/> (in Ukr.).
- Velykochyi, V., & Hasiuk, N. (Eds.). (2005). *Osnovy Muzeieznavstva, Marketynhu ta Reklamno-Informatsiinoi Diialnosti Muzeiv [Fundamentals of Museum Studies, Marketing and Advertising and Information Activities of Museums]*. Ivano-Frankivsk: Plai (in Ukr.).
- Yureneva, T. Yu. (2003). *Muzevedenie [Museology]*. Moscow: Akademicheskii Proekt (in Russ.).

Information about the Authors:

Daria Vasylenko, Senior Lecturer, Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, 20 Pershotravneva Str., Kremenchuk 39600, Ukraine; e-mail: dvoloshka05@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9052-8287> (corresponding author)

Larysa Butko, Assoc. Professor, PhD, Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, Kremenchuk, Ukraine; e-mail: larysabutko@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8817-3381>

Volodymyr Maslak, Professor, DSc, Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, Kremenchuk, Ukraine; e-mail: vimaslak2017@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2898-2400>

Yuliya Domitrak, PhD student, University of Warsaw, Warsaw, Poland; e-mail: juleczka.dom@hotmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6238-4618>